

Sugar in the basal medium was replaced with ten carbon compounds. In the present study, the rate of utilization of carbon compounds was investigated by recording the dry weight of the fungus. The result obtained was recorded in Table 2.

Table 2 shows that *F. oxysporum* was capable of utilizing carbon from different sources. It, however, differed in its choice for the best source of carbon for its growth and sporulation.

Maltose proved to be the best source of carbon for both growth and sporulation. While sucrose, fructose, rhamnose, lactose, galactose supported good growth and sporulation, the minimum growth of mycelium was recorded with raffinose and sorbose.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF DIFFERENT CARBON SOURCES ON GROWTH AND SPORULATION OF *F. oxysporum*

Carbon Sources	Average Dry weight of mycelium in mg.*	Sporulation*
D-Glucose	48.6	Moderate
D-Fructose	62.8	Good
D-Sucrose	58.1	Good
L-Rhamnose	54.5	Moderate
Lactose	51.9	Moderate
Maltose	69.4	Excellent
D-Galactose	60.3	Moderate
Raffinose	23.8	Poor
L-Sorbose	21.0	Poor
D-Xylose	32.9	Moderate

* Average of 3 replications.

Discussion

Hydrogen-ion concentration of the medium has a great importance on metabolic activities of the fungus. Commonly fungi cease to grow below pH 2.0 and beyond pH 9.0 by Wolf and Wolf⁶. Hawker² reported that the growth of *F. fructigenum* on Richard's medium of pH 4.6 gradually raised the pH until the reaction turned strongly alkaline. Sarkar³ reported that fungi *B. theobromae* could grow well at pH 6.5. Hawker² stated that most fungi grow best at neutrane reaction, that is pH 7.00. The present investigation also confirmed the same results in case of *F. oxysporum* which could grow best at pH. 7.0.

So far as carbon requirement is concerned, Bhatnagar and Prasad¹ reported that maltose is the best source of carbon for the growth and sporulation of *F. caeruleum* and *F. soloni*. Srivastava⁴ reported mannose as the best source of carbon for growth of *B. theobromae*. Sarkar³ observed that glucose is the best source of carbon for the development of papaya isolate of *B. theobromae*. But in this experiment it was observed that maltose is the best source of carbon for the growth and sporulations of *F. oxysporum* which causes the wilt disease of *Rauwolfia serpentina*.

References

1. G. C. BHATNAGAR and W. PRASAD, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1968 Sec. B, 163, 168.
2. L. F. HAWKER, "Physiology of Fungi", London University Press Ltd., London, 1950, 169.
3. S. K. SARKAR, Ph.D. Thesis, Ranchi University, Ranchi, India, 1974.
4. M. P. SRIVASTAVA, *Proc. 55th Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1974, III, 313.
5. F. A. WOLF and F. T. WOLF, "The Fungi", John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1974, Vol. 2, p. 289.

Chemical Investigation on Some Mangrove Species. Part I : Genus *Avicennia*

S. GHOSH MAJUMDAR and GOURI PATRA

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan,
Burdwan 713104, West Bengal

Manuscript received 3 December 1975,
revised 13 July 1978, accepted 30 August 1978

THE *Avicennia* is a typical mangrove genus of the family *Verbenaceae*. The object of the present investigation is to ascertain the role of extrinsic factor on the secondary metabolites amongst the species in a genus. Literature survey on genus *Avicennia* revealed the presence of lapacol in *A. tomentosa*¹; betulic acid, taraxerol, taraxerone and triacontane in *A. marina*². Present investigation deals with three *Avicennia* species, viz. *A. officinalis* Linn from Sundarban (West Bengal) and Kakinada (Andhra Pradesh), *A. alba* Bl. and *A. tomentosa* F. from Repalle (A. P.). The constituents isolated or detected from these species by standard procedures are listed in Table 1.

Experimental*

Extraction of stem bark of A. officinalis: Air-dried powdered bark (1.1 Kg) was extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with petroleum ether (5 litres) for 30 hr. The extract was concentrated and filtrated whereby a white solid (4 g) residue (A) was obtained. The filtrate on evaporation furnished deep yellow solid (B) material (4.5 g).

Treatment of solid residue A

It was dissolved in benzene. The dirty white solid, m.p. 280°, separated from supernatant liquid was purified through repeated crystallisations from ethanol. The compound was identified as a betulinic acid, m.p. 300°, $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3350 and 1690 cm^{-1} ; MS: *m/e* 456 (M^+), 433 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{H}_2\text{O}$), 412 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{CO}_2$). Acetate, m.p. 257°, MS: *m/e* 498 (M^+).

* All m.p.'s are uncorrected. Petroleum ether used had b.p. 60-80°.

TABLE 1—CONSTITUENTS OF DIFFERENT *Avicennia* SPECIES

Plant (source)	Part	Compound isolated (%)					
		A	B	C	D	E	F
<i>A. officinalis</i> (Sundarban)	Bark	t	0.018	0.0018	0.027	0.145	0.045
	Leaves	0.015	t	x	0.01	0.05	0.005
<i>A. officinalis</i> (Kakinada)	Bark	0.002	0.01	0.001	0.014	0.025	0.003
	Leaves	0.006	t	x	0.006	0.03	0.002
<i>A. alba</i> (Repalle)	Bark	0.001	0.04	x	0.01	0.016	0.002
	Leaves	0.003	0.006	x	0.012	0.014	0.003
<i>A. tomentosa</i> (Repalle)	Bark	0.001	0.012	0.003	x	0.01	0.001

A=β-Amyrin, B=Taraxerol; C=Taraxerone; D=Betulin;
E=Betulinic acid (isolated as Me-ester), F=Triacontanol,
t=traces; x=absent.

Esterification of the crude acidic fraction (3 g) with CH_3N_2 in cold followed by column chromatography over silica gel furnished only one crystalline substance (1.15 g) using petrol-benzene (1:1) as eluent. The compound on repeated crystallisations from benzene and finally purification through preparative tlc, melted at 217° ; $[\alpha]_D + 5.5^\circ$ (0.72); $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3500 (–OH), 1705 (ester carbonyl), 1640 (double bond), 890 cm^{-1} ($=\text{CH}_2$); MS: m/e 470 (M^+); NMR in CDCl_3 (δ) 0.78–1.65 (methyl and methylene protons), 1.99 (vinylic methyl proton), 2.18 (3–OH), 3.62 (carbomethoxyl protons), 4.58 (3–H), 4.72 (vinyl proton). Acetate, m.p. 198° . It was identified as methyl betulinate, and confirmed by its reduction with LiAlH_4 to betulin, m.p. 255° .

Treatment of residue B :

The ether soluble part (4 g) was separated into neutral and acidic fractions by extraction with cold aqueous 5% NaOH solution. The ether layer was washed and dried (Na_2SO_4). The white sodium salt obtained was suspended in cold water and treated with conc. HCl when crystalline acidic material was obtained. The acid was thoroughly extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was washed and dried.

Treatment of the neutral ether soluble part :

The residue (3 g) after removal of solvent was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over silica gel (250 g). Elution with petrol-benzene (1:1, 1.5 l) afforded a crystalline solid, m.p. 240° , which on recrystallisation from ethanol-benzene melted at $248-9^\circ$; $[\alpha]_D + 6.6^\circ$; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1710 (carbonyl), 1640 cm^{-1} (double bond); MS: m/e 424 (M^+), 300, 285, 204, 189. The compound was characterised as taraxerone (0.02 g). Benzene eluate furnished a mixture which was separated by repeated crystallisation from ethanol-benzene (1:1) and yielded triacontanol (0.05 g), m.p. 82° , $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3025, 718 and 730 cm^{-1} ; MS: m/e 438 (M^+), 423, 405, 392, 354; acetate, m.p. 74° ; and taraxerol (0.2 g); m.p. 268° , $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3400, 1635 and 812 cm^{-1} ; MS:

m/e 426 (M^+), 408, 302, 287, 204, 180; acetate, m.p. 303° . The filtrate was subjected to preparative tlc. The glc study of this compound (0.034 g) showed the presence of β-amyrin. Taraxerol (0.1 g) in acetone (20 ml) was oxidised to taraxerone, m.p. 248° with Jones reagent (2 g of CrO_3 in 1.25 ml conc. $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4/10\text{ ml}$ water).

Later benzene and benzene-chloroform eluates afforded a white crystalline solid (0.3 g). On repeated crystallisation from benzene-ethyl acetate yielded betulin, m.p. 238° ; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3500 cm^{-1} ; MS: m/e 442 (M^+), 42, 424, 411, 385, 288, 257, 248, 220, 207, 189; acetate, m.p. 214° $[\alpha]_D + 25.5^\circ$ (0.43); $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1730, 890 cm^{-1} ($=\text{CH}_2$); NMR in CDCl_3 (δ) 0.88–1.67 (methyl and methylene protons), 1.77 (S, vinylic methyl protons), 2.09 and 2.5 (2- OCOCH_3) 4.03 (m/e , 17- CH_2), 4.47(3-H) 4.75 (mc vinyl proton).

Treatment of acidic fraction :

The ethereal solution (0.3 g) was esterified with ethereal solution of CH_3N_2 . The crude product (0.5 g) on chromatography over silica gel furnished methyl betulinate (0.15 g) m.p. 217° .

Isolation of constituents of the leaves in A. officinalis :

Petrol extract (5 g) of air dried leaves (1 kg) of *A. officinalis* was separated into acidic (2 g) and neutral (2.2 g) fraction. The latter on chromatography over silica gel furnished a mixture of compounds. When eluted with petroleum ether benzene (1:1). Repeated crystallisations from ethanol-benzene yielded triacontanol, m.p. 82° (0.05 g) and β-amyrin, m.p. 195° (0.15 g). $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3240, 1640 and 995, 1375 and 1350 cm^{-1} ; MS: m/e 426 (M^+), 220, 203, 189; acetate, m.p. 212° . The filtrate when subjected to preparative tlc and glc, analysis revealed the presence of taraxerol. The fraction eluted with benzene-chloroform was recrystallised from chloroform and was identified as betulin (0.1 g).

The acidic fraction (1.8 g) was esterified and

NOTES

column chromatography over silica gel furnished methyl betulinate, m.p. 217° (0.5 g) as the only crystalline substance, from petroleum-ether benzene eluate (1 : 1).

Acknowledgement

We are highly indebted to Prof. S. K. Siddhanta for laboratory facilities and encouragement and to Dr. A. Ghosh, Bose Institute, Calcutta, for glc

studies. Thanks are due to Prof. S. K. Talapatra and Prof. P. Sengupta for authentic samples.

References

1. K. BOURNOT, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1914, **251**, 351.
2. K. H. BELL, and H. DUEWELL, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1961, **14**, 662.